

Treatment and prevention of chronic kidney disease

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Abstract: Persistent anomalies in urine composition, aberrant structural features, or Chronic kidney disease is characterized by a diminished excretory renal function, which is suggestive of a loss of nephrons that are functional (CKD). The majority of those who have CKD are also at a higher risk for cardiovascular disease and death. There are numerous places in the globe where people with end-stage renal illness have a hard time gaining access to renal replacement treatment. A low nephron count at birth, nephron loss as individuals age, and acute or chronic kidney damage brought on by toxic exposures or infections are all risk factors that have been linked to the development of chronic kidney disease (CKD) (for example, obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus). Early diagnosis and preventative strategies, therapy aimed at fixing the problem from the ground up (if feasible) to slow the disease's development, and addressing Resulting Methods that lead to persistent nephron loss are the cornerstones of care for CKD patients. Essential components of treatment include blood pressure regulation, renin-angiotensin system inhibition, and disease-specific therapies. Cardiovascular health and quality of life are negatively impacted by CKD complications include anemia, metabolic acidosis, and secondary hyperparathyroidism, all of which need diagnosis and treatment.

Keywords: nephron, acute or chronic kidney damage, development of chronic kidney disease (CKD).

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Introduction

Kidneys are the unsung hero of our health. Some individuals are born without a kidney yet manage to live a normal, healthy life nevertheless. Our kidneys are incredible organs that play a crucial part in overall health maintenance but are often overlooked as necessities. However, if both kidneys fail, as occurs in end-stage renal failure, neither the bones

nor the muscles nor the brain can survive. Damage to the nephrons, tiny filters inside the kidneys, is what causes kidney disease. Because of this, toxins and fluids accumulate within the body.

1. A gradual decline in glomerular function as a result of a disease that has been present in the renal parenchyma for a long time. Renal impairment is present if a person's glomerular filtration rate (GFR) is less than 60 ml/min/1.73 m² for three months in a row, or if it is more than or equal to this value in those who have had kidney impairment for three months or longer.

2. A condition that does not spread from person to person and is often brought on by obesity, diabetes, and hypertension.

3. Usually entails a gradual decline in kidney function, which makes renal replacement treatment necessary in many cases (dialysis or transplantation).

4. Ten percent of the world's population is afflicted by chronic kidney disease (CKD), and millions of people pass away

every year because they do not have access to therapy that is within their price range.

Normal Kidneys and Their Function

The kidneys, which are shaped like beans, are located in the centre of the lower back, one on each side of the spine. Each kidney is responsible for filtering blood and weighs around a quarter of a pound. Each kidney is composed of a glomerulus and a tubule. The tubule, which is connected to the glomerulus, is a small shape like a tube that aids in the filtration and sieving processes.

The ureters are the tubes that go from the kidneys to the bladder. The urinary bladder is the storage organ for urine until it is expelled during urination.

Figure: Schematic Diagram of Kidney

The kidneys filter waste and excess water from the blood, which is their primary function. About two liters of urine are produced daily when the kidneys filter over two hundred liters of blood. Normal metabolic activities, such as the breakdown of working tissues, food, and waste is produced as a consequence of the interaction of other substances.

Figure: Mechanism of renal function

Because of their excellent ability to filter waste items, the kidneys make it safe to consume a wide range of meals, medications, vitamins, supplements, additives, and extra fluids. Additionally, the kidney is a very essential organ in the management of the concentrations of other minerals in the blood, including calcium, sodium, and potassium.

1. Blood is carried into the glomeruli by tiny, leaky blood arteries called capillaries as the first stage of filtering. Waste materials and moisture are removed from the blood, while the capillaries hold on to the red blood cells, proteins, and big molecules.

2. When the blood reaches the tubules, filtering continues. High-functioning cells line the tubules and process the filtrate, reabsorbing water and beneficial chemicals while secreting waste materials.

Some crucial hormones, such as those produced by the kidneys, are as follows:

1. The form of vitamin D that is useful to humans is called calcitriol, which is also known as 1,25-di hydroxyvitamin D. It controls the body's uptake of calcium and phosphorus from the food we eat, which is essential for healthy bone development.

- 2.The peptide hormone erythropoietin (EPO) encourages bone marrow to create RBCs.
- 3.Renin is an enzyme responsible for controlling blood volume and blood pressure.

Epidemiology

The prevalence of chronic kidney disease is high, affecting between 10 and 15 percent of the world's adult population.

- 1.Because of the absence of symptoms in its early to intermediate stages, chronic kidney disease (CKD), it may be difficult to identify the real incidence and prevalence of renal illness that is ongoing (CKD).
- 2.The incidence of CKD in the general population is anywhere between 10 and 14 percent.
- 3.In 2012, chronic kidney disease was responsible for 2,968,600 (one percent) in terms of life-years adjusted for disability and anywhere from 2,546,700 (one percent to three percent) of life-years lost throughout the globe.
- 4.In 2017, the prevalence of chronic kidney disease throughout the globe was 91%, or around 700 million patients.
- 5.There has been a 29.3 percent rise in the incidence of CKD since 1990..
- 6.Dialysis and kidney transplantation have both increased significantly in prevalence as a means of treating the rising prevalence of end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) in the general population (age-standardized incidence of ESKD treated by renal replacement therapy, 43.1 and 34.4 percent, respectively).
- 7.Only five nations — the US, Japan, Germany, Brazil, and Italy — account for the vast bulk the two million individuals throughout the globe who are now receiving treatment for renal failure. Only 12% of the world's population lives in these five nations. About 100 poor nations, home to more than half of the world's population, account for just 20% of those who get treatment.
- 8.In contrast to other major non-communicable illnesses, the worldwide age-standardized death rate for CKD is not decreasing.

Etiology

While there is no universally accepted list of what causes CKD, also known as chronic kidney disease the following are the most prevalent main illnesses in each world region:

- 1.Type 2 diabetes (in 30–50% of cases).
- 2.Type 1 diabetes mellitus (3.9%)..
- 3.Hypertension (27.2%)

After that comes secondary glomerulonephritis or vasculitis (3.1%), hereditary or cystic illnesses (3.1%), plasma cell dyscrasias or neoplasms (2.1%), and finally primary glomerulonephritis (8.2%).

Signs and symptoms of kidney disease

An rise in creatinine levels in the blood or protein levels in the urine is the most common way that CKD is discovered in the early stages, before any symptoms have shown. The decline in renal function may be accompanied by an increase in uncomfortable side effects:

- 1.The risk of hypertension and heart failure is raised when the body retains too much fluid and the kidneys produce vasoactive hormones through the renin-angiotensin system. There is some evidence that uremic toxins cause an increase in the likelihood of developing cardiovascular disease and atherosclerosis seen in those with CKD compared to the general population. Patients who suffer from both CKD and cardiovascular disease have a far more dire prognosis than those who suffer from either condition alone .
- 2.Due to the accumulation of urea, azotemia and, ultimately, uremia will occur . Crystals of urea form on the skin when perspiration evaporates, a result of the high concentration of urea in the body's eccrine sweat ("uremic frost").
- 3.The blood becomes saturated with potassium (a variety of symptoms, including lethargy and possibly deadly cardiac arrhythmias, are associated with hyperkalemia).When the glomerular filtration rate falls below 20-25 ml/min/1.73 m², the patient is said to have chronic kidney disease, the kidneys' capacity to eliminate potassium decreases, leading to hyperkalemia. Lack of insulin and acidemia (which causes potassium to be shifted extracellularly) may both contribute to the development of hyperkalemia in CKD.
- 4.Some people have just minor edema, while others get life-threatening pulmonary edema as a result of fluid excess.
- 5.Inadequate kidney function leads to hyperphosphatemia. Vascular calcification, which is brought on by hyperphosphatemia, adds to an elevated cardiovascular risk. Left ventricular hypertrophy and an increased risk of death have been linked to an increase in the levels of fibroblast growth factor-23 (FGF-23) that are found in circulation, which rises in tandem with a loss in the kidney's ability to excrete phosphate.

6. Due to high fibroblast growth factor (FGF)-23 concentrations and decreased kidney mass, together with parathyroid hormone resistance, hypocalcemia develops. FGF-23 is a powerful inhibitor of 1-alpha-hydroxylase, and osteoclasts are to blame for its increased production (liable for the change that takes place from 25-hydroxycholecalciferol into 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3). Hyperparathyroidism secondary, renal osteodystrophy, and vascular calcification are all symptoms of this condition subsequently develop, all of which further reduce heart function. The very unusual ailment known as calciophylaxis is a direct result.

7. Abnormalities in calcium, phosphorus (phosphate), parathyroid hormone, or vitamin D metabolism; problems with bone turnover, mineralization, volume, linear growth, or strength (kidney osteodystrophy); and calcification of the blood vessels or other soft tissues are all possible outcomes of alterations in mineral and bone metabolism. Outcomes have been shown to be worse for those with CKD who also have problems with their bones and minerals.

8. If the proximal tubule's cells are unable to produce enough ammonia, metabolic acidosis might develop. Hyperkalemia, a result of acidosis, impairs enzyme performance and increases the excitability of cardiac and neural membranes.

9. Patients undergoing hemodialysis are disproportionately affected by anemia. Multiple factors contribute to this condition, but elevated inflammation, decreased erythropoietin, and suppressed bone marrow are all potential culprits. Inadequate erythropoietin production by the kidneys causes hypoproliferative anemia.

10. Sexual problems are widespread among CKD patients, both male and female. Most guys, and especially older men, struggle with a lack of sex desire, an inability to acquire and maintain an erection, and the inability to experience full-fledged orgasmic pleasure. Most women struggle to have sexual desire, and many also deal with a painful menstrual cycle as well as difficulties in sexual performance and enjoyment.

Causes of kidney disease

As of the year 2015, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and glomerulonephritis are all considered to be chronic diseases were the three leading causes of CKD. One third of those with diabetes and one fifth of those with hypertension develop CKD. Idiopathic means "of unclear etiology."

By anatomical location

1. Ischemic nephropathy, hemolytic-uremic syndrome, and vasculitis are three of the conditions that may occur are all examples of small-vessel diseases associated with vascular illness.

2. Glomerular illness encompasses a wide variety of conditions and may be broken down into:

- ❖ Diseases of the glomeruli themselves, such as focal segmental glomerulosclerosis, and IgA nephropathy are examples of these types of kidney conditions (or nephritis).
- ❖ Type 2 diabetes and lupus nephritis are examples of secondary glomerular diseases.

3. Reflux nephropathy and toxic and drug-induced chronic tubulointerstitial nephritis are both forms of tubulointerstitial disease.

4. Obstructive nephropathy, as shown by the presence of The patient was diagnosed with benign prostatic hyperplasia of the prostate gland as well as bilateral kidney stones. Pinworms are a rare but possible cause of obstructive nephropathy, which affects the kidneys.

Other

1. Congenital diseases that are caused by genetic mutations include a condition known as 17q12 microdeletion, as well as polycystic kidney disease.

2. "agricultural nephropathy is a potential name for a novel kind of kidney disease" is what the medical community refers to as "Mesoamerican nephropathy." Mesoamerican nephropathy, commonly known as chronic kidney disease, has been diagnosed in a disproportionately high number of male Central American laborers in the sugar cane fields in the lowlands of El Salvador and Nicaragua, have been observed. This condition is known as the Mesoamerican nephropathy. Long hours of piecework in hot conditions (about 36 degrees Celsius, or 96 degrees Fahrenheit) are a likely contributor [43], as are agricultural chemicals.

Factors Linked to Advanced Chronic Kidney Disease

1. CKD Risk Factors That Cannot Be Modified Older age, being male, and being of an ethnicity other than Caucasian.

2. Chronic kidney disease has risk factors that can be changed.

Classification

A number of different categories may be used to describe chronic renal disease. According to the rate of filtration by the glomeruli (ml/min/1.73 m²), chronic kidney disease is often divided into five phases.

stage 1: >90: kidney injury despite a normal or higher glomerular filtration rate.

stage 2: 60-89: renal injury accompanied with a little decrease in GFR.

stage 3: 30-59: drop in GFR that is just mild.

stage 4: 15-29: significant drop in global fill rate.

stage 5: <15 (or treatment with dialysis): chronic kidney failure (ESKD).

Manifestation Clinical

The clinical manifestations vary greatly from one cause to another..

1.Children who suffer from chronic kidney illness may have a growth problem, oedema, and urine that is the color of cola .

2.Adults may have non-specific symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, a loss of weight, and an increased tendency to fatigue quickly. These symptoms may be brought on by a variety of conditions.

3.Adults who suffer from chronic renal disease are more likely to have high blood pressure.

4.CKD is associated with a loss of muscle. The results of a cross-sectional research point to a prevalence of sarcopenia in older persons living in the community, with greater rates of sarcopenia and severe sarcopenia being reported in more advanced stages of chronic kidney disease (CKD).

5.The SCOPE investigation found that lower urinary tract symptoms were substantially related with elderly people living in the neighborhood are more likely to fall aged 75 years, whereas CKD was not.

Investigations

Evaluation of renal function:

1.Estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR).

2.Electrolytes

3.Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) (urea in the UK)

4.Creatinine levels

General Management:

Adjusting medication dosage for GFR; Arteriovenous fistula or graft implantation for renal replacement treatment.

1.causes of renal failure that can be reversed must be treated.

2.The course of CKD may be slowed by treating risk factors such high blood pressure, protein in the urine, metabolic acidosis, and high cholesterol.

3.When a patient's estimated GFR is less than 30 ml/min/1.73 mt², a referral to a nephrologist is warranted for the purposes of preplanning and initiating renal replacement therapy. Time to talk about dialysis and kidney transplants.^[5]

Treatments exist for chronic kidney disease. Slowing or halting the course of renal disease is feasible with early diagnosis and therapy.

Inter professional team

A multidisciplinary group of doctors, nurses, and other medical staff who are committed to protecting renal function manages kidney failure. There is a high rate of morbidity and death associated with kidney failure, and it costs the healthcare system billions of dollars annually to treat. The only way to reduce renal failure's morbidity and mortality is for team members to talk openly with one another.

1.The role of the renal failure nurse has evolved to include teaching patients about the disease, its symptoms, and how to spot it early.

2.Furthermore, the pharmacist should conduct patient audits on a consistent basis.

3.Physical therapy involves exercise, which the physiotherapist plays a role in.

4.Patients should be monitored closely to detect any decline in renal function.

5.Healthy diet, quitting smoking, and avoiding excessive alcohol use are all recommendations that should be made to the patient.

Final Remark

1. There is a rising and significant net health burden of kidney illness, which is influenced by environmental and socioeconomic inequalities and is fueled by complex connections between communicable and noncommunicable diseases.

2. Although acute, chronic, and end-stage renal disease may have substantial financial consequences, they are typically avoidable and poor outcomes can be postponed or avoided with very low-priced therapies.

Chronic kidney disease

Loss of renal function develops gradually and is typically irreversible in those who have chronic kidney disease. The process takes time, often a few months to a few years. There are five distinct chronic kidney disease phases, each representing a more dire manifestation of the illness. Renal failure is another word for kidney failure since the term "renal" refers to the kidney. Renal insufficiency is a word that is often used to describe kidney conditions that are not severe. When kidney function declines, the body begins to retain the water, waste, and poisonous chemicals that the kidney would typically expel. Anemia, hypertension, acidosis (increased acidity of bodily fluids), cholesterol and fatty acid issues, and bone disease are only a few of the side effects of kidney failure.

Having lost all or almost all of your kidney function, Kidney failure, also known as end-stage kidney disease or renal disease, is the last stage of chronic kidney disease, which is diagnosed at stage 5. Dialysis is required of the majority of patients who have reached this stage of renal impairment or a transplant to survive due to the deadly buildup of fluids, waste, and toxins.

Acute renal failure, in contrast to chronic kidney disease, manifests suddenly, within a matter of days or weeks.

1. Disorders that strike the kidney itself, its blood supply, or major impairments in the kidneys' capacity to excrete urine.

2. The loss of kidney function that occurs with acute renal failure may sometimes be reversed.

3. Some patients are left with permanent scarring, putting them at risk for chronic renal disease and a slow, steady reduction in kidney function.

4. Some people have severe injuries that leave them permanently reliant on dialysis treatments for their failing kidneys.

The development of chronic renal disease might often seem to be unexpectedly quick. However, this gradual deterioration in kidney function has been going on for quite some time.

About one million specialized filtering cells, or nephrons, may be found in each kidney. Injuries to the nephrons result in the loss of their function. Nephrons in good condition are able to take on additional duties for a short period of time. More and more nephrons die off if the harm isn't stopped. After a certain age, the remaining nephrons are unable to filter blood effectively enough to maintain health.

Figure: Physiology Kidney

Calculating your glomerular filtration rate is one approach to assess kidney function (GFR). The GFR is often determined from blood creatinine (pronounced "kree-AT-uh-noon") test results. The GFR is then used to determine the severity of renal disease. From early kidney damage with a normal GFR through end-stage renal failure, there are five phases of kidney disease. You may take steps to mitigate or even halt kidney damage. Medications and behavioral modifications may help you control your condition and improve your quality of life. Chronic kidney disease is also known by the terms renal insufficiency and chronic renal failure.

Figure : Kidney failure

CKD has no early warning signs and is first recognized by an elevation in kidney function, as measured by blood creatinine or urinary protein. As renal function deteriorates:

1. Increased risk of high blood pressure and heart failure is raised when the body experiences fluid overload and the kidneys respond by producing vasoactive hormones via the RAS (renin-angiotensin system).
2. Over time, urea accumulation causes azotemia and then uremia. Sweat contains urea, which crystallizes on the skin as a waste product ("uremic frost").
3. Blood potassium levels rise.
4. There is a reduction in the production of erythropoietin (potentially leading to anemia, which causes fatigue).
5. An excess of fluids may result in a range of symptoms, from mild bloating to life-threatening pulmonary edema.
6. A high phosphate blood level caused by insufficient phosphate loss, or hyperphosphatemia.
7. Hypocalcemia — owing to 1, 25 di hydroxy vitamin D3 insufficiency. 1,25-di hydroxyvitamin D3 deficiency is caused by fibroblast growth factor activation. - In the long run, this may lead to secondary hyperparathyroidism, renal osteodystrophy, and vascular calcification, all of which are conditions that worsen the heart's ability to pump blood.

Accumulation of sulfates, phosphates, uric acid, and other metabolic waste products, which may lead to metabolic acidosis. Because of this, there is a potential for changed enzyme activity as a result of the action of excess acid on enzymes, as well as increased excitability of both cardiac and neuronal membranes as a consequence of the encouragement of hyperkalemia brought about by an excess of acid in the body (acidemia).

People who have conditions that affect their kidneys on a chronic basis because their atherosclerosis progresses more quickly than other people's. Patients who are suffering from both cardiovascular illness and chronic renal disease often have a substantially more dire prognosis than those who are simply suffering from cardiovascular disease.

Public Health Problem of Chronic Kidney Disease

If four requirements are satisfied, a health issue or illness is seen as a public health concern when it affects a significant number of people. The prevalence of illness is firstly quite high. The public feels threatened by this illness because of the toll it takes in lives lost, quality of life diminished, and financial costs incurred. As a second issue, the burden of the problem is not shared equally.

These requirements are met by chronic kidney disease (CKD), making it a relevant public health concern. With regards to the first criteria, more than 385,000 Americans now suffer from ESRD, the stage of chronic kidney disease in which only dialysis or a kidney transplant may prolong life. This amounts to around 11% of the adult U.S. population, or an estimated 19.2 million people. Only 0.22 percent of the population with early CKD is predicted to develop end-stage renal disease.

The toll that CKD exacts is increasing. The incidence and prevalence of ESRD have grown substantially within the past three decades. The number of people on dialysis or who have had a kidney transplant rose from 42,000 in 1980 to 431,000 in 2012, while the number of those diagnosed with ESRD each year rose from around 14,500 to 100,359. CKD is not only costly, but also leads to early morbidity and death and a decline in quality of life. Recent evidence from a variety of

large, diverse populations has linked lower glomerular filtration rates (GFRs) to increased risks of mortality, cardiovascular events, and hospitalization; these risks are lower than those documented in patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD), but still significant. Estimates for the number of fatalities attributable to CKD range from 71,000 in 2000 to 352,000 in 2030. kidney disease was recently placed in the ninth spot on the list of leading causes of death in the United States (CDC). However, this statistic is not an adequate representation of the burden of renal illness since it does not take into consideration the high rates of comorbidity that are seen in the community of people with CKD. Patients who have CKD have a greater risk of passing away due to complications associated with their kidney disease than they have of developing end-stage renal disease. In spite of the fact that chronic kidney disease greatly reduces the average lifespan and has a severe effect on the quality of life, it is commonly disregarded as a serious public health concern in the United States.

There is a significant financial cost to individuals, the healthcare system, and society as a whole associated with treating ESRD. Care for those with kidney failure accounts for 6.4% of all Medicare and Medicaid spending, despite the fact that those with kidney failure make up fewer than 1% of the Medicare population. Overall costs in 2001 surpassed \$22 billion, with Medicare covering around two-thirds and commercial insurers the rest. Health care expenditures for those with CKD are anywhere from 1.6% to 2.4% more than those for the ESRD group, according to data from a major HMO and the US Renal Data System that was collected recently. This staggering number has sparked concerns that the illness is out of control. Second, CKD is a concern because it disproportionately affects people of color, who tend to have worse outcomes and incur greater treatment expenditures than the general population. African Americans and Native Americans face a disproportionate threat. Evidence from throughout the globe indicates that CKD is a major health concern for people all over the world. In the United States, moderate to severely reduced kidney function is present in 11 percent of adults aged 65 and over who do not have diabetes or hypertension. CKD also meets the third and fourth criterion since it is possible to take action on the illness at the community and public health levels. The prevalence of CKD might be reduced with the use of upstream preventative efforts, which are not currently in place.

Symptoms of chronic kidney disease

Because the human body can tolerate even a severe decline in kidney function, most persons with CKD have no symptoms at all. That is to say, humans have much superior kidney function at birth than is strictly essential for life. If just one kidney is functioning, it is usually adequate.

Normal blood and urine tests may detect a change in kidney function. Your kidney function will be monitored via the use of routine blood tests, and any symptoms that you have will be treated to the best of the medical team's abilities.

In most cases, kidney function will be monitored using blood tests to detect any development toward kidney failure (established renal failure, or ERF). A variety of symptoms may present themselves in the event of renal failure.

Knowing the signs and symptoms of renal disease is crucial since they often manifest only when there is very little kidney function remaining.

1. warning signs Insomnia is an indicator that something may be wrong.
2. water retention that causes swelling, most noticeably in the extremities and around the eyes.
3. Discolored or acrid pee, or blood in the toilet.
4. One of the first signs is awakening often throughout the night to urinate. Over time, the occurrences become less frequent.
5. a state of lethargy and exhaustion.
6. Disgust.
7. Headaches.
8. Weakness and pains all over .
9. Chronic high blood pressure is a medical disorder in which blood pressure remains consistently high (caused or exacerbated by water retention). The inability to create red blood cells (anemia) because the kidneys do not produce the necessary hormone (because the kidneys are unable to produce a hormone for the production of red blood cells).
10. A lot of bl Urea buildup causes shortness of breath, irregular pulse, a lack of libido, and a sallow, yellowish complexion in severe instances. Symptoms like hiccups and brain fog show considerably later.
11. nausea
12. male sexual dysfunction characterized by an inability to achieve or sustain an erection (an inability to get or maintain an erection).

These are rather generic symptoms that might be caused by a wide variety of less severe diseases or disorders. The aforementioned symptoms may often be prevented if therapy is started before they become noticeable.

At first, kidney failure symptoms may not present themselves (not producing any symptoms). Kidney disease causes symptoms because the organs are less able to do their jobs of maintaining the body's water and electrolyte balances, flushing out waste.

Chronic Kidney Disease Staging

Stages of Chronic Kidney Disease The following chart was produced by the National Kidney Foundation to illustrate the relationship between the severity of chronic kidney disease and the patient's glomerular filtration rate (GFR).

Stage 1 of Chronic Kidney Disease

Glomerular filtration rate decline is the hallmark of early-stage renal disease (GFR) of 90 ml/min or above, which is comparable to a normal kidney. Diagnosing this illness is challenging since there are absolutely no symptoms. However, tests that can reveal the exact quantity of creatinine or urea in the blood are often advised for diabetic patients. Increases in blood creatinine or urine protein concentration are telltale signs of chronic renal disease. Kidney function may also be evaluated with the use of imaging modalities including MRI, ultrasound, X-ray, and CT scan. Medication may be used to prevent, slow, or even reverse CKD if the condition is caught early on.

There are a number of other methods by which a person may become aware that they have CKD stage 1:

1. Abnormally high blood creatinine and urea levels.
2. There is either blood or protein in the urine.
3. Diagnosis of kidney injury on a contrast X-ray, MRI, or ultrasound.
4. The presence of polycystic kidney disease in one's family (PKD).

The degree of renal damage may be determined by regularly checking the urine protein and serum creatinine levels. The development of kidney disease may be slowed by adopting a healthy lifestyle. People with CKD Stage 1 are encouraged to:

1. Maintain a balanced diet:

- Have a varied grain intake, with whole grains as the primary emphasis, and a diet rich in fresh fruits and vegetables.
- Decide on a diet that is reasonable in total fats while being low in saturated fats and cholesterol.
- Avoid eating too many sugary and salty processed and refined meals.
- Refrain from using salt and other high-sodium items while cooking.
- Maintaining a healthy weight requires daily physical exercise.
- Eat enough calories..
- Meet your daily vitamin and mineral needs by eating a balanced diet.
- Restriction of potassium and phosphorus is often not done until blood levels are very high.

2. Keep their blood pressure at a healthy level

3. Reduce their risk of high blood sugar or diabetes by maintaining a healthy balance.

4. Have their GFR measured with a blood creatinine test at each and every appointment.

5. Medicate as directed by their physician.

6. Maintain a consistent exercise routine.

7. Stop smoking

Although kidney disease cannot be reversed, its progression may be halted or its effects mitigated. Oftentimes, a person's kidneys and overall health may be preserved with the right care and adjustments in lifestyle.

Diagnosis of Chronic Kidney Disease, Stage 2.

When the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) decreases to a level indicative of stage 2 chronic kidney disease (CKD), renal damage becomes noticeable (GFR) falls to between 60 and 89 ml/min. In most cases, there will be no outward manifestations of kidney injury. As a result of the kidneys' ability to perform well even when they are not operating at full

capacity, the majority of persons with stage 2 CKD are unaware of their condition. Testing for anything else, like diabetes or high blood pressure, is frequently how people learn they're at stage 2.

Additional indicators of CKD stage 2 include:

1. Blood creatinine or urea levels that are abnormally high.
2. There is either blood or protein in the urine.
3. Diagnosis of kidney injury on a contrast X-ray, MRI, or ultrasound.
4. The presence of polycystic kidney disease in one's family (PKD).

Monitoring the levels of protein in the urine and serum creatinine on a regular basis may provide information about the severity of kidney injury. Kidney disease may be slowed by adopting a healthy lifestyle. People with CKD stage 2 are encouraged to:

1. Maintain a balanced diet:
 - Have a varied grain intake, with whole grains as the primary emphasis, and a diet rich in fresh fruits and vegetables.
 - Decide on a diet that is reasonable in total fats while being low in saturated fats and cholesterol.
 - Avoid eating too many sugary and salty processed and refined meals.
 - Refrain from using salt and other high-sodium items while cooking.
 - Try to maintain a healthy weight by eating sensibly and exercising often.
 - Restriction of potassium and phosphorus is often not done until blood levels are very high.
2. Keep their blood pressure at a healthy level
3. Reduce their risk of high blood sugar or diabetes by maintaining a healthy balance.
4. Have their GFR measured with a blood creatinine test at each and every appointment.
5. Medicate as directed by their physician.
6. Maintain a consistent exercise routine..
7. Stop smoking.

Although kidney disease cannot be reversed, its progression may be halted or its effects mitigated. Oftentimes, a person's kidneys and overall health may be preserved with the right care and adjustments in lifestyle.

Stage 3 of Chronic Kidney Disease

The onset of symptoms occurs at this point. It's estimated that the GFR ranges from 30 to 59 ml/min. Fatigue and shortness of breath are being experienced by the patient. Swelling in the extremities is a telltale sign that fluids are collecting in places other than the blood and tissues. Alterations in urine color are another telltale sign. Colors like dark orange, crimson, and brown emerge. If a patient reaches stage three, a nephrologist is consulted to determine the source of the condition using a battery of diagnostic tests and provide treatment recommendations. A nutritionist may help someone in this phase choose the diet that works best for them. Pain in the lower back or flanks is a common symptom of polycystic kidney disease.

Stage 3 may be the onset of symptoms, such as:

Fatigue: Anemia is a frequent cause of fatigue in persons with CKD.

Too much fluid: It is possible that the kidneys will lose their regulation of intracellular fluid levels. Edema, or swelling, may manifest in a variety of places, including the lower legs, hands, and face/eyes. Someone may have difficulty breathing if they drink too much liquids.

Urination changes: If there is protein in the urine, it may be frothy, and if there is blood, the urine may be a dark orange, brown, tea, or red color. Increased or decreased urination or nighttime toilet visits are also possible..

Kidney pain: While most individuals with chronic kidney disease (CKD) don't have kidney pain, those who have conditions like polycystic kidney disease (PKD) or infections that affect the kidneys could feel discomfort in their lower back..

Sleep problems: It might be difficult for some individuals to go to sleep or remain asleep. Restless legs, muscular

twitches, and itching are all possible causes of insomnia.

The National Kidney Foundation advises patients in stage 3 to visit a nephrologist. For the purpose of diagnosing and treating renal disease, nephrologists conduct a variety of tests and exams on their patients. For the nephrologist, it's all about helping the patient extend the useful life of their kidneys. A referral to a dietician is another option for someone in stage 3. Diet is a crucial element of therapy, therefore the dietician will look at the patient's test findings and make recommendations based on them. Maintaining healthy kidney function and general health is one of the many benefits of eating a balanced diet.

Stage symptoms consist of things like:

Fatigue: Anemia is a frequent cause of fatigue in persons with CKD..

Too much fluid: It is possible that the kidneys will lose their regulation of intracellular fluid levels. Edema, or swelling, may manifest in a variety of places, including the lower legs, hands, and face/eyes. Extreme dehydration may cause a person to get breathless..

Urination changes: If there is protein in the urine, it may be frothy, and if there is blood, the urine may be a dark orange, brown, tea, or red color. Individuals may pee often or seldom, or awaken frequently during the night to urinate..

Kidney pain: However, certain kidney diseases, kidneys are located in the back, thus any problems with them, including polycystic kidney disease (PKD) or an infection, may lead to severe back pain.

Sleep problems: It might be difficult for some individuals to go to sleep or remain asleep. Restless legs, muscular twitches, and itching are all possible causes of insomnia.

Nausea: Nausea and vomiting are common indicators of chronic renal disease.

Taste changes: There's a chance that food won't taste quite right.

Sneezes and coughs: If urea is building up in the body, it might be detected in exhaled air.

Loss of appetite: Many individuals at this phase don't feel like eating, and some even report experiencing a metallic taste or poor breath..

Concentration issues: CKD may cause cognitive impairments, such as difficulty concentrating on tasks like checkbook balance or reading the newspaper..

Nerve problems: You may have chronic kidney disease if you have numbness or tingling in your toes and fingers..

Once symptoms reach stage 4, medical attention from a nephrologist is required. The nephrologist does a physical examination and may request diagnostic testing to help in formulating a treatment plan.

Regular checkups with a physician are recommended for those with stage 4 CKD at least every three months. The kidneys' functionality will be evaluated using a battery of blood tests measuring levels of creatinine, hemoglobin, calcium, and phosphorus. Additionally, the doctor will keep an eye on things like blood sugar levels and blood pressure. Assisting the patient in maintaining kidney function for as long as feasible, and preparing the patient for dialysis or a kidney transplant, are all part of the nephrologist's job description.

A kidney transplant, hemodialysis, or peritoneal dialysis (PD) are all options for those with stage 4 CKD who will require therapy. People who choose for hemodialysis will learn about vascular access. After surgery, the arteriovenous

(AV) fistula and AV graft require a few months to fully develop. Dialysis preparation often begins with a conversation between the nephrologist and their Stage 4 patient regarding the AV fistula procedure and the perks that come with it.

A dietician may be recommended for someone in Stage 4. Diet is a crucial element of therapy, therefore the dietician will look at the patient's test findings and make recommendations based on them. Maintaining healthy kidney function and general wellbeing with nutrition alone. Dietitians often advocate cutting down on protein during stage 4 to assist prevent the accumulation of waste products made of protein. Reducing phosphorus intake may assist maintain healthy levels of blood phosphorus or parathyroid hormone and so protect against renal bone disease. Phosphorus restriction may also assist maintain renal function. In CKD stage 4, potassium intake may be limited if serum potassium levels are high. If the patient has diabetes, the nutritionist will also give them advice on how to cut down on their carbohydrate intake. People who have high blood pressure or fluid retention may also be advised to follow a low-sodium diet. Vitamins that dissolve in water may be useful to take as a supplement. There may be a daily maximum of 100 milligrams (mg) for vitamin C pills. Reduced renal function may necessitate avoiding some vitamins and minerals owing to the increased danger of toxic blood levels. The nutritionist may suggest passing on those supplements you find at the store unless your nephrologist gives the go light. Consultation with a qualified renal dietician is useful since dietary needs fluctuate with the progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD).

Eating well during stage 4 chronic kidney disease may:

1. Grain, fruit, and vegetable intake, with possible restrictions on If you have high phosphorus or potassium levels, eat more whole grains and certain fruits and vegetables.
2. Moderate total fat intake with a low saturated fat intake is recommended for those with high cholesterol, diabetes, or cardiovascular disease.
3. Restricting protein consumption to an amount commensurate with one's caloric requirements as established by a dietician.
4. Water-soluble vitamin B complex and vitamin C intake at the Recommended Daily Allowance.
5. Supplementation with vitamin D and iron may be adjusted to meet the needs of each person..
6. Phosphorus restriction if PTH or phosphorus levels in the blood are high.
7. Lowered calcium intake if blood calcium levels are high.
8. If blood potassium levels are high, it may be necessary to reduce intake.

Patients in stage 4 should maintain a good blood pressure and glucose level. It's possible that kidney function may be preserved with strict adherence to a doctor-prescribed medication regimen.

Stage 5 of Chronic Kidney Disease

Fifth stage is defined as total renal failure. GFR is less than 15 ml/min; in certain situations, it may be 0. Additional symptoms that appear in the fourth stage include headaches and a change in skin tone. When a patient's kidneys fail, they urinate less often or not at all. The most effective therapy for stage 4 CKD is a kidney transplant, while hemodialysis or peritoneal dialysis may be continued for some time.

Stage 5 chronic kidney disease symptoms might include::

1. Appetite loss.
2. Nausea or vomiting.
3. Headaches.
4. Being tired.
5. Having trouble focusing.
6. Itching.
7. Eliminating very little or no urine.
8. An increase in circumference, most noticeably at the eyeballs and ankles.
9. Muscle cramps.
10. tingling sensation in the limbs.
11. Variations in skin tone.
12. Pigmentation of the skin that's become darker.

As waste and fluids accumulate in the body without being flushed out by the kidneys, a general malaise sets in. Aside from controlling blood pressure, creating a hormone that aids in making bone health and red blood cell production through vitamin D activation, the kidneys also have additional duties that they are unable to fulfill.[23]

You should make an appointment with a nephrologist right away if you have been told that you have CKD stage 5. This medical professional specializes in treating renal illness and performing kidney dialysis or transplantation. The doctor will propose an access for dialysis and assist you select between hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis (PD), and a kidney transplant as your treatment options. In general, your nephrologist will be in charge of designing your treatment strategy and supervising your healthcare team.

Causes of Chronic Kidney Disease

It is common practice to classify the causes in order of where the harm was inflicted.

Renal failure that persists over time is called chronic. A majority of cases of chronic renal failure may be attributed to:

1. Uncontrolled diabetes.
2. Low blood pressure control.
3. Chronic.

rarer forms of glomerulonephritis:

1. Disorder of the Kidneys Characterized by Multiple Cysts.
2. This condition is known as reflux nephropathy..
3. Urinary calculi.
4. Prostate disease.

Prerenal causes The kidneys' prerenal (pre = before, renal = kidney) causes stem from inadequate vascular supply. A few examples of factors that occur before the kidneys are affected include:

1. Low blood volume (hypovolemia) as a result of hemorrhaging..
2. Deficiency in bodily fluids, leading to dehydration (vomiting, diarrhea, sweating, fever).
3. Inadequate fluid intake.
4. Drugs like diuretics (often called "water pills") may result in significant hydration loss.
5. Deficiency of renal perfusion caused by occlusion of a both the renal artery and vein.

Direct kidney injury is called a renal cause:

Sepsis: Infection induces inflammation and renal failure by taxing the body's immune system to its breaking point. Urinary tract infections almost seldom cause this.

Medications: Ibuprofen and naproxen are two examples of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs that have the potential to damage renal function. Iodine is also utilized in radiography dye injections.

Rhabdomyolysis: When there is a lot of muscle breakdown going on, the byproducts of the broken down muscle fibers can't be filtered out by the kidneys.

Multiple Myeloma

The kidney's filtration mechanism, the glomeruli, becomes inflamed, causing acute glomerulonephritis. Several disorders, such as SLE, Wegener's granulomatosis, and Goodpasture syndrome, may trigger this inflammatory response.

Post renal causes Those that occur after the kidneys (post-renal):

1. If the kidneys keep making urine yet the bladder or ureters are full, the urine will build up and cause back pressure. The kidneys can no longer filter blood when arterial pressure is too high.
2. The urethra may become blocked due to prostate enlargement or cancer, preventing the bladder from emptying.
3. Abdominal tumors that press on the ureters and cause obstruction.
4. Kidney stones

Common causes of Chronic kidney Disease:

CKD may be caused by any of a variety of disorders that either directly harm the kidneys or interfere with their normal functioning. In the United Kingdom, there are three main triggers that likely account for three-quarters of all adult instances of chronic kidney disease:

Diabetes. One of the most frequent diabetes-related complications is renal failure..

High blood pressure. Uncontrolled or inadequately managed hypertension is a key contributor to chronic kidney disease. However, since the kidney is involved in blood pressure control, CKD may also lead to hypertension. Hypertension affects over 90% of those with CKD stages 3-5.

Ageing kidneys. It seems that kidney function naturally decreases with aging. More over half of those aged 75 and above have chronic kidney disease. Unless other renal issues arise, such as diabetic kidney disease, the CKD often does not advance beyond the intermediate stage in these patients.

This is by no means an exhaustive list, and there may be many other less prevalent reasons as well.

Uncommon Causes of Chronic Kidney Disease:

The nephrons, leading to kidney disease in people with diabetes. Keeping blood glucose levels within a reasonable range is the most important thing you can do to treat or avoid this kidney disease. By lowering blood pressure, one may halt the development of, or at least delay the course of, renal disease.

Polycystic kidney disease

This kind of kidney disease is passed on from generation to generation. It leads to the development of many cysts inside the kidneys. Sometimes PKD doesn't lead to chronic kidney disease, but often the cysts consume the rest of the kidney, severely impairing its ability to filter blood.

Most cases of polycystic kidney disease are autosomal dominant, meaning that the illness is passed on from a parent to a child with a 50% chance of developing the condition. A person with this condition may show no symptoms at all, while others may not do so until they are well into their 30s or 40s.

Kidney damage caused by these conditions may sometimes be detected prenatally. Childhood symptoms often include slowed development, vomiting, and back or side discomfort. Blood or protein in the urine, as well as elevated blood pressure and anemia, are further warning signs. Moreover, imaging is being employed to detect cysts in kids and teenagers.

Pyelonephritis

Infection, often bacterial, is the root cause of this kidney disease. There are a number of potential reasons for pyelonephritis, but a blockage in urine drainage is usually to blame. The ureters, which carry urine from the kidney to the bladder, might be blocked due to a kidney stone, scarring in the ureters, a clogged bladder, or a tumor.

If this condition is brought on by repeated infections, the bacteria causing it may develop resistance to treatment over time, making it possible for the symptoms to reoccur. In order to completely get rid of the illness, you must finish the whole course of antibiotics.

Glomerular Diseases

Autoimmune illnesses, infections, and sclerotic diseases are all forms of kidney disease that fall under this umbrella. Glomeruli, which are small blood arteries inside the nephrons, are damaged.

Diabetic nephropathy, systemic lupus erythematosus, Alport syndrome, and IgA nephropathy are all examples of disorders that fall under this umbrella. HIV and bacterial endocarditis are only two of the many common illnesses that may lead to kidney damage.

Proteinuria (excess protein in the urine) and hematuria (blood in the urine) are the hallmarks of both kidney conditions.

Diabetes Insipidus

The inability of the kidneys to efficiently preserve water while removing waste products and excess fluid from the circulation is a hallmark of this condition. A lack of the hormone antidiuretic hormone (ADH), also known as vasopressin, may have a role in this condition.

It may also develop if the kidneys aren't wired up to react to ADH because of a lack of biochemical receptors at birth. This condition is called nephrogenic diabetic insipidus. Both diseases may be treated successfully.

Central diabetes insipidus occurs when either the pituitary gland or the hypothalamus in the brain sustains injury. Injuries to the head, infections, surgical procedures, and tumors are all potential causes of brain damage.

Diagnosis of Kidney disease

In chronic renal disease, ultrasonography of the kidneys may be used for diagnosis and monitoring. Increased echogenicity of the cortex is a common finding after any pathologic alteration, such as sclerosis of the glomeruli; atrophy of the tubules; interstitial fibrosis; and inflammation. Kidney echogenicity should be correlated with liver or spleen echogenicity. Finally, as the condition advances, kidney size decreases and cortical thinning are common observations. However, the size of one's kidneys is inversely proportional to one's height, and short people tend to have tiny kidneys; consequently, kidney size cannot be used alone as a trustworthy measure. Elevated echogenicity and decreased cortical thickness are hallmarks of glomerulo nephritic chronic kidney disease. The kidney length is shown on the US picture by a plus sign and a dotted line for measurement purposes. Kidney failure; nephrotic syndrome. The kidney is hyperechoic and there is no clear separation between the cortex and the medulla. Kidney size reduction and localized cortical thinning as a result of chronic pyelonephritis. The US graphic depicts the kidney length measurement as a plus sign and a dashed line.

Increased echogenicity, a lack of structural separation between the renal parenchyma and renal sinus, and a shrunken kidney all indicate end-stage chronic kidney disease. The '+' and dotted line seen on the US picture depict the method used to quantify the size of the kidneys.

Treatment of Kidney Disease

Kidney failure is a medical emergency that must be avoided at all costs. Kidney damage and other organ failure are catastrophic consequences of chronic diseases like hypertension and diabetes. Maintaining healthy levels of blood sugar and blood pressure requires constant vigilance throughout life. The diagnosis of a condition is crucial in determining the appropriate therapy.

Once kidney failure has been diagnosed, stopping its progression is of paramount importance. In the absence of intervention, renal disease would inevitably lead to death, but with prompt diagnosis and treatment, kidney function may be maintained, if not improved.

Diet

People with renal disease need to pay special attention to what they eat. The best way to figure out what meals are good or bad for you is to go to a dietitian. Water, salt, and potassium should probably be ingested in moderation since the kidneys have a hard time filtering out large amounts. Bananas, dried apricots, and low-sodium food options are all good options for getting your daily dose of potassium. In addition to being linked to calcium metabolism, phosphorus levels may also be increased in renal failure, despite its often-overlooked significance. The loss of calcium from the bones due to an excess of phosphorus may lead to osteoporosis and breakage. Milk, cheese, almonds, and cola drinks are all good examples of high-phosphorus foods.

Medications

Some of the symptoms of renal failure may be managed with medication.

1. Calcitriol (Rocaltrol), sevelamer (Altace), and calcium carbonate (Caltrate) are examples of drugs used to reduce phosphorus levels (Renagel)]
2. Erythropoietin and darbepoetin are hormones that help the body make more red blood cells. (Aranesp)]
3. Making RBCs (red blood cells) (iron supplements).
4. Hypertension treatment.
5. Vitamins.

Dialysis

Patients with renal failure are often treated with a process called dialysis, in which an artificial kidney is used to filter the blood and remove waste products and excess water. Dialysis is an option for patients with chronic kidney disease stage 5, which may be caused by either a sudden loss of kidney function or a gradual loss of function over time.

Types of dialysis

Hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis, hemofiltration, hemodiafiltration, and intestinal dialysis are the five basic dialysis methods, with hemofiltration and hemodiafiltration serving as additional methods (secondary).

health. Dietitians typically suggest 0.8 grams of protein per kilogram of body weight for stage 3, the same amount they recommend for healthy persons overall. The quality of the protein consumed may need further scrutiny. Phosphorus restriction may also assist maintain renal function. If blood calcium levels are already high, more may not be absorbed. Potassium intake is not limited in CKD stage 3 unless blood potassium levels are very high. If the patient has diabetes, the nutritionist will also give them advice on how to cut down on their carbohydrate intake. People who have high blood pressure or fluid retention may also be advised to follow a low-sodium diet. Vitamins that dissolve in water may be useful to take as a supplement. There may be a daily maximum of 100 milligrams (mg) for vitamin C pills. It is possible that some vitamins and minerals should be avoided due to the risk of toxic blood levels. The nutritionist may suggest passing on those supplements you find at the store unless your nephrologist gives the go light. A licensed renal dietician might be beneficial since the diet for CKD patients changes as the disease progresses.

Some research suggests that a balanced diet for CKD stage 3:

1. Weighing in on potential dietary restrictions for whole grains and select produce if blood tests reveal higher-than-normal levels of phosphorus or potassium.
2. Moderate total fat intake with a low saturated fat intake is recommended for those with high cholesterol, diabetes, or cardiovascular disease.
3. Refraining from high-sodium refined and processed meals and cooking with less salt or low-sodium components.
4. Attempting to achieve a healthy weight by maintaining a balanced diet and regular exercise.
5. Maintaining a diet rich in high-quality protein within the Daily Recommended Intake range.
6. Water-soluble vitamin B complex and vitamin C intake at the Recommended Daily Allowance.
7. Vitamin D and iron dosages may be adjusted based on each person's needs.
8. Phosphorus restriction if PTH or phosphorus levels in the blood are high.
9. Lowered calcium intake if blood calcium levels are high.
10. Once blood potassium levels are normal, they are seldom if ever lowered.

Stage 4 of Chronic Kidney Disease

Further decline in GFR is associated with an expansion of clinical manifestations. The patient's breath smells terrible because his blood urea levels are rising. Patients in the fourth stage of chronic kidney disease often report feeling sick and losing their appetite. He suffers from a wide range of nerve issues and gradually loses the capacity to focus. In stage four, the GFR ranges from 15 to 29 ml/min. At current time, the most prevalent therapies are hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis. Many nephrologists also advise a kidney transplant if the patient's GFR is below 15 ml/min. Weakness, fatigue, difficulty breathing, and widespread edema might develop. Undiagnosed or neglected, potentially fatal conditions may worsen.

1. Toxic cardiac rhythm abnormalities are linked to hyperkalemia, or an inability to eliminate potassium, which causes blood potassium levels to rise (arrhythmias).
2. A range of organs, including the brain (encephalopathy), the lining of the heart (pericarditis), and the muscles (due to low calcium levels), may be negatively impacted by elevated urea levels in the blood (uremia) (hypocalcemia).
3. Erythropoietin levels below the optimal range fail to stimulate bone marrow production of red blood cells, which may lead to anemia and subsequent generalized weakness. Having a low red blood cell count means your blood can't carry as much oxygen to your cells, reducing their efficiency. The increased usage of anaerobic metabolism by cells due to a lack of oxygen also causes an increase in acid generation that the failing kidneys are unable to neutralize.
4. Loss of appetite, drowsiness, and exhaustion are symptoms of a buildup of waste materials in the blood. As this worsens, the person's ability to think clearly may diminish, and coma may set in.
5. As the kidneys are unable to neutralize the increasing acid load, the lungs speed up their breathing to expel carbon dioxide and reduce the acidity. High blood pressure from fluid retention is possible, the buildup of fluid in the lungs and subsequent congestive heart failure.

Hemodialysis

When a patient is undergoing hemodialysis, their blood is pushed through a dialyzer's blood compartment and into contact with a semipermeable membrane.

Thousands of microscopic synthetic hollow threads make up the dialyzer. The fiber membrane serves as a semipermeable barrier. Water and wastes go between the blood and the dialysis solution, while blood carries oxygen and nutrients to the tissues. Following purification, blood is recirculated back into the body. A higher hydrostatic pressure over the dialyzer membrane causes ultrafiltration. The dialysate chamber of the dialyzer is often subjected to a negative pressure in order to do this. Through the application of a pressure gradient, blood is able to exchange water and dissolved solutes with dialysate, resulting in the elimination of several liters of surplus fluid in the course of a normal 3- to 5-hour therapy. Due to Medicare payment regulations in the United States, hemodialysis is normally administered in a dialysis clinic three times per week. However, as of 2007, over 2,500 Americans were dialyzing at home more regularly for varying treatment durations. The therapeutic advantages of dialyzing 5–7 times weekly for 6–8 hours have been proven in several studies. Nocturnal daily hemodialysis is a kind of hemodialysis that has been found to reduce the need for phosphate binders and increase clearance of molecules of all sizes. Home dialysis is a versatile modality, thus treatment plans may be altered on a daily or weekly basis, and patients commonly do these lengthy treatments while resting. Both longer treatment durations and more frequent sessions have been demonstrated to have positive therapeutic effects in research.

Peritoneal dialysis

Peritoneal dialysis Process

The peritoneal cavity is the abdominal cavity enclosing the intestine. The peritoneum, also known as borders abdominal space (sometimes called peritoneal space) and protects the organs located inside it from injury (stomach, spleen, liver, and intestines). After the dialysate has had time to soak up the waste. This "exchange" occurs many times daily, often four to five times. One exchange occurs when the abdomen is filled with dialysate and then emptied. "Dialysis involves the removal of toxins, chemicals, and excess fluid from the patient's blood into a solution called dialysate. After a period of time called "dwell," during which the dialysate is infused with the patient's waste products and excess fluid, the dialysate is drained. Osmosis is responsible for ultrafiltration; the high glucose content in the dialysis solution creates an osmotic pressure that draws fluid out of the blood and into the dialysate. Because of this, there is a net loss of fluid. Even though hemodialysis, it achieves results that are equivalent in terms of waste product elimination and salt and water removal. The patient does peritoneal dialysis at home. Assistance is useful, but not necessary. It does provide patients more flexibility in their schedules by allowing them to do dialysis at home or on the road with a minimum of specialist equipment.

Hemofiltration

Although it works on a similar basis as hemodialysis, hemofiltration is a distinct medical modality. Water is forced over the highly permeable membrane at high velocity by an applied pressure gradient, carrying along with it comes a plethora of dissolved chemicals, some of which have molecular weights too enormous to be effectively removed by hemodialysis.

Hemodiafiltration

Several techniques that do both hemodialysis and hemofiltration are together known as hemodiafiltration.

Combining hemodialysis with hemofiltration creates a new treatment called hemodiafiltration. Both hemodialysis and hemofiltration may be avoided throughout treatment, which is a major benefit of this method.

Intestinal dialysis

Soluble fibers like acacia fiber, which are broken down by colonic bacteria, are added to the diet during intestinal dialysis. The proliferation of these microbes increases the quantity of nitrogen lost through feces. Instead, you might try

drinking Polyethylene glycol and mannitol solutions, which do not absorb, at a rate of 1 to 1.5 liters every four hours.

Starting indications

A number of variables influence whether or not a patient with renal insufficiency should begin dialysis or hemofiltration. Reasons to Dialyze Chronically:

- 1.The onset of renal failure symptoms.
- 2.Reduced ability to filter blood via the kidneys (low glomerular filtration rate; GFR 10-15 ml/min/1.73 m2) Dialysis is started at an earlier age in diabetics.
- 3.Medical challenges in regulating fluid excess, serum potassium, and/or serum phosphorus in patients with extremely low glomerular filtration rates.

Study design

A descriptive design was conducted to asses the knowledge regarding chronic kidney disease obtain data from the Squire Hospital, Al Baraka Kidney Foundation of Dhaka district.

Sample selection

The place of study was selected on the basis of considering following points

- 1.Location- Dhaka district
- 2.The Al Baraka General Hospital & Research Centre, National Institute of Kidney Diseases & Urology and IBN Sina Dialysis Center
 - Obtaining good number of patients at a period of time.

Procedure of data collection

The data was collected face to face interview were taking after schedule work and whenever they wish to give interview. The research his/herself to the questions and the interview answer the questionnaire spontaneity.

CKD Prevention Finding the reason

CKD is more common among the elderly, and it also disproportionately affects members of numerous minority groups. About a quarter of individuals in the UK on dialysis don't know what caused their kidney failure. Patients under the age of 65 requiring renal replacement treatment are more likely to be affected by glomerulonephritis and pyelonephritis, respectively, than are older males, who are more likely to be affected by diabetes, hypertension, and renovascular disease. [38] Sometimes, kidney damage may be avoided if the underlying condition is treated, therefore it's crucial to determine what's causing it, which often involves imaging and sometimes a renal biopsy.

For the survey and data collection one questionnaire was designed. The model of questionnaire is include below- Survey on Treatment and Prevention of Disease of the Kidneys, Chronic in Bangladesh Results of patient’s survey outline

Questionnaire for the patients	Total No. Patients Surveyed N=73	Frequency	Response & pattern (%)
1.Gender	73		
Male		30	41%
Female		43	59%
2. What is your age?	73		
10-20		03	4.1%
21-30		05	6.8%

31-40		07	9.5%
41-50		14	19.1%
51-60		20	27.4%
61-70		15	20.5%
71+		09	12.3%
3. Sign & symptoms of CKD in Bangladesh?			
	73		
Fever		55	75.3%
Leg swelling		42	57.5%
Pain		65	89%
Poly Urination		60	82.1%
Irritation		52	71.2%
Others		20	27.3%
4. What is the age of onset of the Disease?			
	73		
10-20		03	4.1%
21-30		05	6.8%
31-40		07	9.5%
41-50		19	26%
51-60		25	34.2%
61-70		10	13.7%
71+		04	5.4%
5. Chronic kidney disease in Bangladeshi families.			
	73		

Yes		28	38.3%
No		45	61.6%
6. Cause of CKD in Bangladesh.			
	73		
Glomerulonephritis		55	75.3%
Type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus		61	83.5%
High blood pressure		65	89%
Enlarged prostate, strictures (narrowing), or cancers.		25	34.2%
Clogging and hardening of the arteries		23	31.5%
Repeated urinary infections		35	48%
Others		25	34.2%
7. What was the Diagnostic?			
	73		
Creatinine Test		73	100%
Hemoglobin test		40	54.8%

RBC test		35	48%
Others		27	37%

8. Management profile of CKD in Bangladesh.	73		
Taken Protein food		50	68.4%
Regular measurement of serum creatinine.		30	41.1%
Physical Exercise.		58	79.4%
Avoid Smoking		45	61.6%
Others		17	23.2%

9. What is Treatment of CKD in Bangladesh?	73		
Omeprazole		35	48%
Cytoxan		18	24.6%
Bisoprolol		25	34.2%
Furosemide		46	63%
Domperidon		20	27.4%
Others		10	13.6%
10. What is the stage of CKD in Bangladesh?	73		
1 st stage		01	1.3%
2 nd stage		20	27.3%
3 rd stage		39	53.4%
4 th stage		09	12.3%
5 th stage		05	6.8%
11. Dislysis is needed of CKD in Bangladesh?	73		
N/A		39	53.4%
Hemodialysis		26	35.6%
Paritonal dialysis		08	10.9%
12. Have any co-existing disease of CKD in Bangladesh	100		
High Blood Pressure		65	89%
Diabetes Mellitus		60	82.1%
Anemia		26	35.6%
Others		20	27.3%

Patients survey result.

Q. 1: Relation of gender with CKD.

Table 1: Gender of CKD Patients

Observation of CKD patients	Male	Female
Infected Patients	30	43
% of infection	41%	59%

Figure: Gender of CKD Patients

Comment: Females were more prone to CKD.

Correlation of age with CKD.

Table 2: Age of CKD Patients

Observation of CKD patients	10-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-71	70+
Affected Patients	03	05	07	14	20	15	09
% of Affection	4.1%	6.8%	9.5%	19.1%	27.4%	20.5%	12.3%

Q.3: Signs and symptoms of CKD.

Table 3: Signs and Symptoms of CKD Patients

Signs and symptoms of CKD patients	Fever	Leg swelling	Pain	Poly Urination	Irritation	Others
Infected patients	55	42	65	60	52	20
% of infection	75.3%	57.5%	89%	82.1%	71.2%	27.3%

Figure: Sign and Symptoms of CKD patients

Q.4: Age of onset of the disease.

Table 4: Onset of Stage of CKD Patients

Observation of CKD patients	10-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-71	70+
Affected Patients	03	05	07	19	25	10	04
% of affection	4.1%	6.8%	9.5%	26%	34.2%	13.7%	5.4%

Figure: Onset of Stage of CKD Patients

Q.5: Do you have any family history of kidney disease.

Table 5: Family History of CKD

Family history of CKD	Yes	No
Response	28	45
% of response	38.3%	61.6%

Figure: Family History of CKD

Q.6: Causes of CKD.

Causes of CKD Patients

Observation of CKD patients	Glomerulo nephritis	Type 1 and type 2 diabetes Mellitus	High Blood Pressure	Enlarged Prostate, Strictures (narrowing), or Cancers.	Clogging and Hardening of the Arteries	Repeated Urinary Infections	Others
Infected Patients	55	61	65	25	23	35	25
% of Infections	75.3%	83.5%	89%	34.2%	31.5%	48%	34.2%

Figure: Causes of CKD Patients

Q.7: Result of CKD.

Table 7: Diagnostic Test of CKD Patients

Diagnostic test for CKD	Creatinine test	Hemoglobin test	RBC test	Others
Performed test	73	40	35	27
% of test	100%	54.8%	48%	37%

Figure: Diagnostic Test of CKD Patients

Q.8: The management profile.

Management Profile of CKD Patients

Management for CKD	Taken protein food	Regular Measurement of Serum Creatinine	Physical Exercise.	Avoid Smoking	Others
Response	50	30	58	45	17
% of response	68.4%	41.1%	79.4%	61.6%	23.2%

Q.9: The Treatment profile.

Drugs for CKD	Omeprazole	Cytoxan	Bisoprolol	Furosemide	Domperidone	Others
Response of drugs	35	18	25	46	20	10
% of Response	48%	24.6%	34.2%	63%	27.4%	13.6%

Figure: Treatment of CKD Patients

Q.10: The stage of CKD.

Stage of CKD	1 st stage	2 nd stage	3 rd stage	4 th stage	5 th stage
Infected Patients	01	20	39	09	05
% of Infection	1.3%	27.3%	53.4%	12.3%	6.8%

Figure: Stage of CKD Patients

Q.11: Dialysis process for CKD.

Table 11: Dialysis Process of CKD

Dialysis for CKD	Hemodialysis	Peritoneal dialysis	N/A
Response	26	08	39
% of response	35.6%	10.9%	53.4%

Q.12: Co-existing disease of CKD.

Table 12: Co-existing Disease of CKD Patients

Co-existing disease of CKD	High blood pressure	Diabetes mellitus	Anemia	Others
Disease	65	60	26	20
% of disease	89%	82.1%	35.6%	27.3%

Figure: Co-existing Disease of CKD Patients

Conclusion:

In most of the developing countries including Bangladesh, One of humanity's gravest ails is chronic kidney disease. This survey is conducted to observe the Chronic Kidney Disease at Dhaka City in Bangladesh. In this survey, 73 patients were interviewed and they were asked according to the questions.

In this survey. It was seen from patient survey that (59%) female and (41%) male were affected by the Chronic Kidney Disease. it was seen that the most affected (27.4%) patients were between the ages of 51-60. where the most of disease were in the age of 51-60.[49]

In this survey, it was seen that patient's very common sign and symptoms are fever ,poly urination and pain. Mostly blood test and creatinine test are performed for detecting infections. In this survey that Glomerulonephritis is the most prevalent underlying condition, High Blood Pressure and Diabetes Mellitus for the detecting infection.

It was reported from patient's survey that Furosemide, Omeprazole, Bisoprolol, Domperidone etc where the most frequently prescribed medicine for the CKD patients and most of the patients are not taken any dialysis in Dhaka City.

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is more widespread and consequential than previously recognized. The majority of persons with CKD have mild to moderate forms, which do not need intensive care. The danger of developing end-stage renal failure is often outweighed by the adverse effects on the patient's cardiovascular system caused by renal illness.

In current century, CKD has created a fear and has become a great concern to the medical science as the fetal disease. But it is a fact of console that, proper treatment reduce the severity and suffering of CKD, even it can be completely prevent by maintaining hygiene and being conscious.

A conscious society and proper treatment procedure can gift us a disease free beautiful earth

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